

Fundamentals of Science Education

Course number	: Se Ed 3001	Course duration	: 150 hrs
Nature of the course	: Theoretical	Number of periods	: 180
Full mark	: 100	Periods per week	: 6
Pass mark	: 35	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is an introductory course on science education. The course contains nine units that deal with various aspects of science education including education technology and activities for skill development.

General Objective

This course is designed to provide the prospective school science teachers with the fundamental knowledge of the nature of science, school science curriculum, learning psychology, management of laboratory and science equipment. It also aims to provide them with the basic skills in the organization of school science laboratories and science clubs, improvisation of school science equipment and evaluation of science textbooks.

Specific Objectives

On completion of this course the prospective school science teachers will be able to

- explain the basic concepts of nature of science.
- distinguish between science and science education.
- recognize the importance of science in everyday life and school curriculum.
- explain scientific attitude and ways of developing it.
- explain the responsibilities of a science teacher.
- explain the taxonomy of educational objectives.
- write behavioral objectives for science education.
- explain the concepts of cognitive development as propounded by Jean Piaget and Jerome Bruner and their implications in science teaching.

- explain the principles and approaches of curriculum organization.
- report the critical analysis of existing school science curriculum as well as selected international science curriculum projects.
- explain the characteristic features of science textbooks.
- evaluate the existing school science textbooks.
- explain the characteristic features of Chemistry, Biology, Physics and multiple science laboratories.
- explain the safety precautions to be observed in science laboratory.
- write a report on the present position of science laboratory in Nepal.
- explain the importance of practical work in science teaching.
- construct improvised apparatus for science teaching and explain its importance.
- explain the role of educational technology in science learning/teaching.
- explain the trends in science teaching.
- explain the role of science clubs in the skill development of science teachers.

Course Contents

Unit 1: Nature of Science	(12 periods)
Unit 2: Objectives	(20 periods)
Unit 3: Psychology of learning	(20 periods)
Unit 4: Curriculum	(36 periods)
Unit 5: Textbooks	(12 periods)
Unit 6: Science Laboratory	(15 periods)
Unit 7: Science Equipment and Materials	(45 periods)
Unit 8: Education Technology	(10 periods)
Unit 9: Skill Development through Science Club Activities	(10 periods)

Course Contents in Detail

Unit 1: Nature of Science

- 1.1 Definition of science
- 1.2 Distinctiveness of science and science education
- 1.3 Implications of the nature of science in science teaching
- 1.4 Impact of science on modern living
- 1.5 Place of science in school curriculum
- 1.6 Values of science in everyday life

- 1.7 Scientific attitudes
- 1.8 Responsibilities of the science teacher

Unit 2: Objectives

- 2.1 Differences between aims and objectives
- 2.2 Taxonomy of educational objectives
 - 2.2.1 Cognitive domain
 - 2.2.2 Affective domain
 - 2.2.3 Psychomotor domain
- 2.3 Behavioral objectives
 - 2.3.1 Definition
 - 2.3.2 Functions of behavioral objectives
 - 2.3.3 Limitations of behavioral objectives
 - 2.3.4 Writing behavioral objectives
- 2.4 Critical study of secondary school science objectives in Nepal

Unit 3: Psychology of Learning

- 3.1 Learning
 - 3.1.1 Definition of learning
 - 3.1.2 Characteristics of learning
 - 3.1.3 Factors which increase and improve learning
- 3.2 Motivation of learning
 - 3.2.1 Nature of motivation
 - 3.2.2 Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation
 - 3.2.3 Motivation factors and science teachers
- 3.3 Cognitive development and Jean Piaget
 - 3.3.1 Stages of cognitive development
 - 3.3.2 Factors affecting development from one stage to another

Unit 4: Curriculum

- 4.1 Meaning of Curriculum
- 4.2 Factors influencing curriculum
- 4.3 Principles of curriculum organization
- 4.4 Approaches to curriculum organization
 - 4.4.1 Topical approach
 - 4.4.2 Logical and psychological approach
 - 4.4.3 Subject-centred approach
 - 4.4.4 Activity-centred approach
 - 4.4.5 Environment based approach
 - 4.4.6 Integrated approach

- 4.5 Criteria of a good science curriculum
- 4.6 Science curriculum development process and its application in Nepal
- 4.7 Curriculum evaluation
- 4.8 Critical analysis of innovative international science curriculum projects
 - 4.8.1 B.S.C.S.
 - 4.8.2 CHEM-study
 - 4.8.3 P.S.S.C.
 - 4.8.4 Nuffield O-level
- 4.9 Critical analysis of existing school science curriculum

Unit 5: Textbooks

- 5.1 Science textbooks
- 5.2 Functions of science textbooks
- 5.3 Characteristics of a good science textbook
- 5.4 Textbook selection in Nepal
- 5.5 Critical analysis of the existing secondary school science textbooks in Nepal

Unit 6: Science Laboratory

- 6.1 Importance of laboratory work
- 6.2 Layout of a science laboratory
- 6.3 Characteristics of a chemistry laboratory
- 6.4 Characteristics of a physics laboratory
- 6.5 Characteristics of a biology laboratory
- 6.6 Characteristics of a multipurpose science laboratory
- 6.7 Safety measures in a science lab: common accidents and their remedies
- 6.8 Critical study of the present position of science lab in Nepal

Unit 7: Science Equipment and Materials

- 7.1 Importance of practical work
- 7.2 Science kits
- 7.3 Importance of improvised materials
- 7.4 Construction of improvised materials

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Unit 8: Education Technology

- 8.1 Meaning of education technology
- 8.2 Education technology and its adaptation in science teaching
- 8.3 Hardware and software of education technology
- 8.4 Education technology, science education and science teaching

Unit 9: Skill Development through Science Club Activities

- 9.1 Importance of the science club
- 9.2 Organization of a science club
- 9.3 Activities of a science club

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Seminar, report writing and presentation
- Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 100 marks

Unitwise mark distribution

Units 1 to 5 : 55 marks

Units 6 to 9 : 45 marks

Questionwise mark distribution

20 multiple-choice questions : $20 \times 1 = 20$ marks

2 long-answer questions : $2 \times 12 = 24$ marks

8 short-answer questions : $8 \times 7 = 56$ marks

Prescribed Textbooks

1. Gupta, V. K. Teaching and Learning of Science and Technology. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House, 1995.
2. Sharma, R. C. Modern Science Teaching. New Delhi: Dhanpat Rai & Sons, 1987.

References

1. Gupta, S. K. Teaching Physical Sciences in Secondary Schools. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers, 1981.
2. UNESCO Handbook for Biology Teachers Paris: UNESCO, 1986.
3. Victor, E. Science for the Elementary School. New York: Macmillan Publishing Co., 1980
4. Yadav, M. S. Teaching of Science. New Delhi: Anmol Publications, 1992.

Science Practical Activities

Course number	: Sc Ed 3002	Course duration	: 200 hrs
Nature of the course	: Practical	Number of periods	: 240
Full mark	: 100	Periods per week	: $3 \times 3 = 9$
Pass mark	: 40 %	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This course exclusively deals with the practical activities of science education. The course consists of three units. The first unit deals with practical experiments in various areas of physics, chemistry and biology. The second unit is concerned with the preparation of instructional materials such as charts and models. The improvisation of science equipment is taken up in the last unit.

General Objective

This course is designed with a view to developing practical skills needed to identify and design activities for effective teaching of school science.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the teacher trainees will be able to

- identify, design and carry out practical activities in various areas of physics, chemistry and biology.
- prepare charts and models for science teaching.
- improvise school science equipment with locally available resources.
- identify problems on science education and suggest measures to overcome them.

Course Contents

Unit 1: Experiments in Physics, Chemistry and Biology	(48+48+48 = 144 periods)
Unit 2: Preparations of Charts and Models	(36+24 = 60 periods)
Unit 3: Improvisation of School Science Equipment	(36 periods)

Course Contents in Detail

Unit 1: Experiments in Physics, Chemistry and Biology

- 1.1 Experiments in physics
 - 1.1.1 Tracing lines of force around a bar magnet and finding out the pole strength of the magnet
 - 1.1.2 Finding out the external and internal volume of a tube
 - 1.1.3 Finding out the diameter of a given ball
 - 1.1.4 Finding out the density of a given substance
 - 1.1.5 Finding out the value of 'g'
 - 1.1.6 Finding out the focal length of a given concave mirror
 - 1.1.7 Finding out the focal length of a given convex mirror
 - 1.1.8 Determining the focal length of a given convex lens
 - 1.1.9 Determining the refraction index of a prism
 - 1.1.10 Determining the melting point of a given solid
 - 1.1.11 Verifying the Archimedes principle
 - 1.1.12 Verifying the laws of reflection
- 1.2 Experiments in chemistry
 - 1.2.1 Designing apparatus and studying electrolysis of water
 - 1.2.2 Studying neutralization reaction and recovery of the products
 - 1.2.3 Designing apparatus and preparing H_2 , O_2 , N_2 , CO_2 and NH_3 gases and determining their properties
 - 1.2.4 Investigating the relationship between solubility and temperature
 - 1.2.5 Performing crystallization and recovering crystals of copper sulphate
 - 1.2.6 Studying the rate of chemical reaction of hydrolysis of methyl acetate
 - 1.2.7 Performing simple tests for carbohydrates, proteins, fats and oils
 - 1.2.8 Studying colour pigments of leaves and flowers by paper chromatography
 - 1.2.9 Investigating water pollutants

- 1.3 Experiments in biology
 - 1.3.1 Collecting and identifying common plants and animals
 - 1.3.2 Preparing herbarium of the collected plants
 - 1.3.3 Preserving the collected plants and animals
 - 1.3.4 Preparing temporary slides of plant materials
 - 1.3.5 Dissecting and studying the internal organs of frog and earthworm
 - 1.3.6 Preparing temporary slides of (i) setae and nephridia of earthworm and (ii) striped muscles and blood of frog
 - 1.3.7 Studying pond ecosystem

Unit 2: Preparation of Charts and Models

2.1 Charts

- 2.1.1 Life cycle of fern
- 2.1.2 Life cycle of mushroom
- 2.1.3 Classification of plants
- 2.1.4 Classification of animals
- 2.1.5 Life cycle of mosquito
- 2.1.6 Life cycle of silkworm
- 2.1.7 Somatic cell division
- 2.1.8 Meiotic cell division
- 2.1.9 Skeletal system of human body
- 2.1.10 Circulatory system of human body
- 2.1.11 Periodic table
- 2.1.12 Preparing hydrogen gas
- 2.1.13 Preparing oxygen gas
- 2.1.14 Preparing nitrogen gas
- 2.1.15 Preparing carbon dioxide gas
- 2.1.16 Preparing ammonia gas

2.2 Models

- 2.2.1 Plant cell and animal cell
- 2.2.2 Heart
- 2.2.3 Brain
- 2.2.4 DNA and RNA
- 2.2.5 Aquarium
- 2.2.6 Molecular models

Unit 3: Improvisation of School Science Equipment

- 3.1 Osmometer
- 3.2 Demonstration of composition of water
- 3.3 Demonstration of electroplating of metals
- 3.4 Demonstration of expansion of solids, liquids and gases
- 3.5 Demonstrating that metals conduct heat at different rates
- 3.6 Compass needle
- 3.7 Dip circle
- 3.8 Leaf electroscope
- 3.9 Simple reflecting telescope
- 3.10 Periscope
- 3.11 Prism

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Seminar, report writing and presentation
 - Field work
 - Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 100 marks

Internal assessment : 20 marks (Pass mark : 8)

Mark distribution :

Experiment performance : 16 marks

Regularity and record : 4 marks

External examination : 80 marks (Pass mark : 32)

Unitwise mark distribution

Unit 1 : 48 marks

Unit 2 : 20 marks

Unit 3 : 12 marks

Note: Trainees are required to pass internal assessment and external examination separately.

Prescribed Textbooks

1. Giri, S., D. N. Bajpai and O. P. Pandey. Practical Chemistry. New Delhi : S. Chand and Co.
2. Pandey, B. P. Modern Practical Botany Volumes I & II. S. Chand and Co., 1995.
3. Shrestha, U. P. Physics Practical Guide. Kathamandu: Ratna Pustak Bhandar, 2050 B.S.
4. Verma, P. S. A Manual of Practical Zoology: Invertebrates. New Delhi: S. Chand and Company, 1995.
5. Verma, P. S. A Manual of Practical Zoology: Chordates. New Delhi: S. Chand and Company, 1995.

References

1. Chhatwal, G. R., M. Katyal and S. P. Dudeja. Experiments in Chemistry. New Delhi : Tata McGraw Hill.
2. Kumar, V. Practical Biology. New Delhi: Dhanpat Rai and Sons, 1992.
3. Sthapit, M. K. Elementary Practical Chemistry. Kathmandu: Taleju Prakashan, 1995.
4. UNESCO Source Book for Science Teaching. Paris: UNESCO, 1963.

Science Teaching Methodology

Course number	: Sc Ed 3003	Course duration	: 150 hrs
Nature of the course	: Theoretical	Number of periods	: 180
Full mark	: 100	Periods per week	: 6
Pass mark	: 35	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is an introductory course on science teaching methods and strategies. The course consists of seven units that deal with various pedagogical aspects including instructional planning, microteaching and evaluation.

General Objective

This course is designed with a view to providing the prospective school science teachers with a sound knowledge of teaching methods and strategies and of planning and evaluation of science instruction. Special emphasis is laid on the development of observational and pedagogical skills through microteaching and team teaching.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the prospective school science teachers will be able to

- explain the characteristics of various methods of teaching science.
- apply different types of methods in teaching science lessons.
- explain and practise microteaching and team teaching.
- differentiate between measurement and evaluation and explain their functions.
- explain attributes of a good achievement test.
- construct and administer tests, mark and score them and analyze the results.
- analyze critically the present examination system in general and S.L.C. examination in particular, specially with reference to science education.
- explain the need, importance and elements of unit plans and lesson plans.
- develop unit and lesson plans on selected topics of science teaching and apply them in actual classroom teaching.

- explain the competencies expected of science teachers.
- explain the importance of the evaluation of science teachers and their teaching.
- develop and use a format for science class observation and analyze its findings.

Course Contents

Unit 1: Appraisal of Various Teaching Methods and Strategies	(20 periods)
Unit 2: Evaluation	(40 periods)
Unit 3: Instructional Planning	(20 periods)
Unit 4: Microteaching and Team Teaching	(20 periods)
Unit 5: Evaluation of Teachers and their Teaching	(25 periods)
Unit 6: Trends in Science Teaching	(10 periods)
Unit 7: Science Teacher Education	(45 periods)

Course Contents in Detail

Unit 1: Appraisal of Various Teaching Methods and Strategies

- 1.1 Guiding principles for selecting teaching strategies
- 1.2 Methods of teaching science: characteristic features, strengths and weaknesses
 - 1.2.1 Lecture method
 - 1.2.2 Demonstration method
 - 1.2.3 Lecture cum demonstration method
 - 1.2.4 Inquiry method
 - 1.2.5 Project method

Unit 2: Evaluation

- 2.1 Introduction to evaluation
- 2.2 Measurement and evaluation
- 2.3 Functions of evaluation
 - 2.3.1 Diagnostic functions
 - 2.3.2 Formative functions
 - 2.3.3 Summative functions
- 2.4 Tools of evaluation
- 2.5 Types of test items
- 2.6 Attributes of a good achievement test
- 2.7 Item analysis

- 2.8 Critical analysis of S.L.C. questions
- 2.9 Critical analysis of the present system of S.L.C. examination

Unit 3: Instructional Planning

- 3.1 Unit plan
 - 3.1.1 Need and importance of a unit plan
 - 3.1.2 Elements of a unit plan
 - 3.1.3 Development of unit plans on selected topics
- 3.2 Lesson plan
 - 3.2.1 Need and importance of a lesson plan
 - 3.2.2 Elements of a lesson plan
 - 3.2.3 Format of a lesson plan
 - 3.2.4 Development of lesson plans on selected topics
 - 3.2.5 Application of the developed lesson plans

Unit 4: Microteaching and Team Teaching

- 4.1 Microteaching
 - 4.1.1 Objectives of microteaching
 - 4.1.2 Components of microteaching
 - 4.1.3 Planning and practice of microteaching on selected topics
- 4.2 Team Teaching
 - 4.2.1 Objectives of team teaching
 - 4.2.2 Steps of team teaching
 - 4.2.3 Planning and practice of team teaching on selected topics

Unit 5: Evaluation of Teachers and their Teaching

- 5.1 Importance of evaluation of science teachers and their teaching
- 5.2 Competencies expected of science teachers
- 5.3 Development of a format for science class observation
- 5.4 Observation of science classes using the developed format

Unit 6: Trends in Science Teaching

- 6.1 Trends evolved after the first Russian sputnik 1957
- 6.2 The changing trends in school science teaching during 1980s

S.L.C.

Unit 7: Science Teacher Education

7.1 Teaching of secondary school science lessons on selected topics in

- Physics
- Chemistry
- Biology

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Seminar, report writing and presentation
- Field work
- Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 100 marks

Unitwise mark distribution

Units 1, 2 and 6 : 40 marks

Units 3, 4, 5 and 7 : 60 marks

Questionwise mark distribution

20 multiple-choice questions : $20 \times 1 = 20$ marks

2 long-answer questions : $2 \times 12 = 24$ marks

8 short-answer questions : $8 \times 7 = 56$ marks

Prescribed Textbooks

1. Gupta, V. K. Teaching and Learning of Science and Technology. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House, 1995.
2. Sharma, R. C. Modern Science Teaching. New Delhi: Dhanpat Rai & Sons, 1987.

References

1. Gupta, S. K. Teaching Physical Sciences in Secondary Schools. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers, 1981.
2. UNESCO Handbook for Biology Teachers. Paris: UNESCO, 1986.
3. Victor, E. Science for the Elementary School. New York: Macmillan, 1980.
4. Yadav, M. S. Teaching of Science. New Delhi: Anmol Publications, 1992.

General Science

Course number	: Sc Ed 3001E (G)	Course duration	: 200 hrs (Th120 + Pr80)
Nature of the course	: Theoretical cum Practical	Number of periods	: 240 (Th144 + Pr96)
Full mark	: 100 (Th80+Pr20)	Periods per week	: Th5 + Pr6 (2x3)
Pass mark	: Th28 + Pr8	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is a course on general science. The course has two parts: theoretical (80%) and practical (20%) and the trainees are required to pass both the parts separately. The theoretical part consists of ten units that deal with various aspects of general science in considerable depth and detail. The practical part deals with the practical applications of the theoretical part.

General Objective

This course is designed to provide the prospective non-science teachers with the basic and useful concepts of biological, chemical and physical sciences including much needed knowledge about environmental pollution and its controlling measures.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the trainees will be able to

- explain the importance of study of biology.
- explain different kinds of plants and animals.
- identify different kinds of cells.
- explain function and reproduction of cells.
- explain structure and function of chromosomes.
- explain the structure of Watson and Crick model of DNA.
- explain the function of RNA and DNA.
- explain Mendellion inheritance in human beings.
- explain autosomal dominant and recessive traits.
- explain human traits as shown by single gene pair and multiple alleles and polygenes.

- explain transport system in plants.
- explain the factors influencing transpiration in plants.
- explain the movement of sugar (translocation) in plants.
- explain respiration in plants and animals.
- explain dyes as chemicals.
- explain antibiotics, antipyretic, analgesic and tranquilizer in terms of chemicals.
- explain different kinds of fertilizers.
- explain the effects of pesticides in environment.
- explain different kinds of carbohydrates, proteins and lipids.
- explain the properties of carbohydrates, proteins and lipids.
- explain different kinds of chemical reactions.
- write chemical equations.
- explain sources, types and effects of air, water and land pollutants.
- explain the source and effects of noise pollution.
- explain the controlled measures for air, water, land and noise pollution.
- explain different kinds and forms of energy.
- explain the transformation and conservation of energy.
- explain the nature of light.
- explain laws of reflection and refraction.
- explain dispersion of light
- explain the nature of current electricity.
- explain the electric circuits in series and parallel.
- explain the uses and safety rules of electricity.

Course Contents

Unit 1: The Sphere of Life	(10 periods)
Unit 2: The Language of Life	(15 periods)
Unit 3: The Systems of Life	(15 periods)
Unit 4: Chemistry in the Service of Man	(10 periods)
Unit 5: Bio-molecules	(15 periods)
Unit 6: Chemical Reactions and Equations	(15 periods)
Unit 7: Environmental Pollution	(24 periods)
Unit 8: Energy	(10 periods)
Unit 9: Light	(15 periods)
Unit 10: Current Electricity	(15 periods)

Course Contents in Detail**Unit 1: The Sphere of Life**

- 1.1 Introduction to the living world
 - 1.1.1 The origin of biology
 - 1.1.2 Biology today
- 1.2 The diversity of life
 - 1.2.1 Classification of plants
 - 1.2.2 Classification of animals

Unit 2: The Language of Life

- 2.1 Cells
 - 2.1.1 Structure of cells
 - 2.1.2 Functions of cells
 - 2.1.3 Reproduction of cells
- 2.2 Genetics and heredity
 - 2.2.1 Chromosomes
 - introduction
 - structure of chromosome
 - functions of chromosome
 - 2.2.2 Genes
 - introduction
 - structure of DNA (Watson and Crick model)
 - functions of RNA and DNA
 - 2.2.3 Heredity
 - introduction
 - Mendelian inheritance in humans
 - Autosomal dominant and recessive traits
 - some human traits determined by a single gene pair
 - some human traits determined by multiple alleles and polygenes

Unit 3: The Systems of Life

- 3.1 Transport system in plants
 - 3.1.1 Movement of water and minerals
 - 3.1.2 Factors influencing transpiration
 - 3.1.3 Movement of sugars (translocation)
- 3.2 Respiration
 - 3.2.1 Respiration in plants
 - 3.2.2 Respiration in animals

- 3.3 Reproduction
 - 3.3.1 Reproduction in plants
 - 3.3.2 Reproduction in animals

Unit 4: Chemistry in the Service of Man

- 4.1 Chemicals in dyes
 - 4.1.1 Chemical constituent of dyes
 - 4.1.2 Dyes on the basis of their applications
- 4.2 Chemical medicines
 - 4.2.1 Antibiotics
 - 4.2.2 Antipyretics
 - 4.2.3 Analgesics
 - 4.2.4 Tranquilizers
- 4.3 Chemical fertilizers
 - 4.3.1 Introduction
 - 4.3.2 Types of fertilizers
- 4.4 Pesticides
 - 4.4.1 Introduction
 - 4.4.2 Effects of pesticides

Unit 5: Bio-molecules

- 5.1 Carbohydrates
 - 5.1.1 Introduction
 - 5.1.2 Types of carbohydrates
 - 5.1.3 Properties of carbohydrates
- 5.2 Proteins
 - 5.2.1 Introduction
 - 5.2.2 Types of proteins
 - 5.2.3 Properties of proteins
- 5.3 Lipids
 - 5.3.1 Introduction
 - 5.3.2 Types of lipids
 - 5.3.3 Properties of lipids

Unit 6: Chemical Reactions and Equations

- 6.1 Chemical equations
 - 6.1.1 Introduction
 - 6.1.2 Writing chemical equations

- 6.2 Chemical reactions
 - 6.2.1 Introduction
 - 6.2.2 Types of chemical reactions
 - combination reaction
 - decomposition reaction
 - redox reaction
 - precipitation reaction
 - neutralization reaction

Unit 7: Environmental Pollution

- 7.1 Introduction
- 7.2 Air pollution
 - 7.2.1 Sources of air pollutants
 - 7.2.2 Types of air pollutants
 - 7.2.3 Effects of air pollutants
 - 7.2.4 Control measures
- 7.3 Water pollution
 - 7.3.1 Sources of water pollutants
 - 7.3.2 Types of water pollutants
 - 7.3.3 Effects of water pollutants
 - 7.3.4 Control measures
- 7.4 Land pollution
 - 7.4.1 Sources of land pollution
 - 7.4.2 Types of land pollution
 - 7.4.3 Effects of land pollution
 - 7.4.4 Control measures
- 7.5 Noise pollution
 - 7.5.1 Sources of noise pollution
 - 7.5.2 Effects of noise pollution
 - 7.5.3 Control measures

Unit 8: Energy

- 8.1 Introduction
- 8.2 Kinds of energy
 - 8.2.1 Kinetic energy
 - 8.2.2 Potential energy
- 8.3 Forms of energy
 - 8.3.1 Mechanical energy
 - 8.3.2 Heat energy

- 8.3.3 Electrical energy
- 8.3.4 Wave energy
- 8.3.5 Chemical energy
- 8.3.6 Nuclear energy
- 8.4 Transformation of energy
- 8.5 Conservation of energy

Unit 9: Light

- 9.1 The nature of light
 - 9.1.1 Introduction
 - 9.1.2 Light travels in straight lines
 - 9.1.3 Transparent, translucent and opaque materials
 - 9.1.4 Shadows
 - 9.1.5 Sources of light
 - 9.1.6 Measurement of light
- 9.2 The reflection of light
 - 9.2.1 Laws of reflection
- 9.3 The refraction of light
 - 9.3.1 Laws of refraction
- 9.4 Prism
 - 9.4.1 Dispersion of light

Unit 10: Current Electricity

- 10.1 The nature current electricity
- 10.2 The simple electric circuit
- 10.3 Conductors and non-conductors
- 10.4 Switches
- 10.5 Series and parallel circuits
- 10.6 Electric units of measurement
- 10.7 Uses of electricity
- 10.8 Safety rules

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Field work
- Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 80 marks

(Pass mark : 28)

Unitwise mark distribution

Units 1 to 3 : 22 marks

Units 4 to 7 : 36 marks

Units 8 to 10 : 22 marks

Practical examination : 20 marks

(Pass mark : 8)

Mark distribution

Regular performance and record : 4 marks

Experiments in final examination : 12 marks

Oral examination : 4 marks

Prescribed Textbooks

1. Arora, B. B. and A. Sabharwal. Modern's ABC of Biology, Volumes I and II. New Delhi: Modern Publishers.
2. Dara, S. S. Environmental Chemistry. New Delhi: S. Chand and Company, 1997.
3. Gupta, S. K. Modern's ABC of Physics. New Delhi : New Delhi: Modern Publishers, 1997.
4. Jauhar, S. P. Modern's ABC of Chemistry, Volumes I & II. New Delhi: Modern Publishers, 1998.

References

1. Aggarwal, R. C. Modern Inorganic Chemistry. Allahabad: Kitab Mahal, 1979.
2. Bhatia, K. N. Modern Approach to Botany. New Delhi: Surya Publication, 1991.
3. Curtis, H. and N. S. Barnes. Invitation to Botany. New York: Worth Publishers, 1985.
4. Green, N. P. O., G. W. Stout and D. J. Taylor. Biological Science. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996.
5. Gupta, S. K. and J. M. Pradhan. A Textbook of Physics. New Delhi: Surya Publication, 1993.
6. Matthews, P. Advanced Chemistry. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1992.

7. Mix, M. C., P. Farber and K. I. King. Biology, the Network of Life. USA: Harper Collins Publishers.
8. Peters, E. I. Introduction to Chemical Principles. New York: CBS College Publishing, 1982.
9. Ross, J. S. and K. J. W. Wilson. Foundation of Anatomy and Physiology. ELBS.
10. Rowell, G. and S. Herbert. Physics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995.
11. Sharma, K. K. and L. K. Sharma. A Textbook of Physical Chemistry. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House, 1986.
12. Shukla, R.S. and P.S. Chandel. Cytogenetics, Evolution and Plant Breeding. New Delhi: S. Chand and Company.
13. Subramanyam, N. and B. Lal. Principles of Physics. New Delhi: S.Chand & Co., 1989.

Practical

Course Contents

(96 periods)

1. Study of museum specimen of plants
2. Study of museum specimen of animals
3. Identification of given plants
4. Identification of given animals
5. Observation of various kinds of cells for the study of
 - cell structures and organells
 - mitosis and meiosis cell divisions
 - chromosome
6. Preparation of temporary slides of plant cells
7. Study of transpiration phenomenon
8. Study of movement of water in plants
9. Study of aerobic and anaerobic respiration in plants
10. Identification of carbohydrates
11. Identification of proteins
12. Study of Redox reaction
13. Study of neutralisation reaction
14. Study of air pollutants
15. Study of water pollutants
16. Study of laws of reflection

17. Study of laws of refraction
18. Study of dispersion of light by prism
19. Study of electric appliances in series and parallel
20. Construction of simple galvanometer and study its role as electricity detector

Prescribed Textbooks

1. Giri, S., D. N. Bajpai and O. P. Pandey. Practical Chemistry. New Delhi : S. Chand and Co.
2. Kumar, V. Practical Biology. New Delhi: Dhanpat Rai and Sons. 1992.
3. Shrestha, U. P. Physics Practical Guide. Kathmandu: Ratna Pustak Bhandar, 2050 B.S.

References

1. Chhatwal, G. R., M. Katyal and S. P. Dudeja. Experiments in Chemistry. New Delhi : Tata McGraw Hill.
2. Pandey, B. P. Modern Practical Botany Volumes I & II. New Delhi: S. Chand and Co., 1995.
3. Sthapit, M. K. Elementary Practical Chemistry. Kathmandu: Taleju Prakashan, 1995.
4. Verma, P. S. A Manual of Practical Zoology: Invertebrates. New Delhi: S. Chand and Company, 1995.
5. Verma, P. S. A Manual of Practical Zoology: Chordates. New Delhi: S. Chand and Company, 1995.

Physics

Course number	: Sc Ed 3001E (S)	Course duration	: 200 hrs (Th120 + Pr80)
Nature of the course	: Theoretical cum Practical	Number of periods	: 240 (Th144 + Pr96)
Full mark	: 100 (Th80 + Pr20)	Periods per week	: Th5 + Pr6 (2x3)
Pass mark	: Th28 + Pr8	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is a special course in physics. The course has two parts: theoretical (80%) and practical (20%) and the trainees are required to pass both the parts separately. The theoretical part consists of six units that deal with various aspects of physics in considerable depth and detail. The practical part deals with the practical applications of the theoretical part.

General Objective

This course is designed to provide the prospective school science teachers with in-depth knowledge of physics so that they can run the physics classes of secondary level with greater confidence and efficacy. The course also aims at developing manipulative skills needed for practical pedagogical activities in physics.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the trainees will be able to

- apply the fundamental and derived units.
- explain Newton's laws of motion.
- explain the working principle of machine.
- explain work done by constant and varying forces.
- explain different kinds of energy.
- explain the measurement of energy.
- explain the principle of conservation of energy.
- explain units and dimensions of power.
- distinguish between work and power.

- explain Pascal's law and hydraulic lift.
- explain the Archimedes principle
- distinguish between heat and temperature.
- explain the working of different types of thermometer.
- explain the principles of thermal expansion.
- explain the principles of transfer of heat.
- explain the reflection of light at plane and curved surfaces.
- explain the refraction of light at plane surfaces and through prisms and lenses.
- explain dispersion of light through prism.
- explain the wave theory of light.
- explain the principles of simple and compound microscope.
- explain the principles of astronomical, terrestrial and Galileian telescopes.
- explain atomic view of magnetism.
- explain lines of magnetic field, magnetic pole strength, magnetic length and magnetic dipole moments.
- explain Gauss's law of magnetism.
- explain magnetic elements of the earth.
- explain tangent law and tangent galvanometer.
- explain deflection and oscillation magnetometer.
- explain the classification of magnetic elements.
- explain the properties of magnetic elements.
- explain wave motion.
- explain transverse and longitudinal wave motion.
- explain characteristics of wave motion.
- explain velocity of sound.
- explain the factors affecting the speed of sound.
- explain reflection and refraction of sound.

Course Contents

Unit 1: Mechanics	(25 periods)
Unit 2: Thermometry and Thermal Expansion	(20 periods)
Unit 3: Light	(35 periods)
Unit 4: Current Electricity	(20 periods)
Unit 5: Magnetism	(20 periods)
Unit 6: Sound	(24 periods)

Course Contents in Detail

Unit 1: Mechanics

- 1.1 Measurement
 - 1.1.1 Fundamental and derived units
 - 1.1.2 Measurement of length
 - indirect methods for long distance
 - indirect methods for short distance
 - 1.1.3 Measurement of time
 - techniques of measurement of time
 - 1.1.4 Measurement of mass
 - inertial mass and its measurement
 - gravitational mass and its measurement
- 1.2 Newton's laws of motion
 - 1.2.1 Newton's first law of motion
 - linear momentum and its conservation
 - 1.2.2 Newton's second law of motion
 - consequences of Newton's second law
 - 1.2.3 Impulse
 - applications of concepts of impulse
 - 1.2.4 Newton's third law of motion
 - illustration of third law of motion
- 1.3 Machines
 - 1.3.1 Simple machine and principle of work
 - 1.3.2 Mechanical advantage, velocity ratio and efficiency
 - 1.3.3 Lever
 - types
 - applications
 - 1.3.4 Principles of wheel and axle
 - 1.3.5 Pulleys
 - fixed pulley
 - movable pulley
- 1.4 Work, energy and power
 - 1.4.1 Work
 - definition
 - work done by a constant force
 - work done by a varying force
 - conservative and non-conservative force

1.4.2 Energy

- definition and kinds of energy
- measurement of kinetic and potential energy.
- conversion of gravitational potential and kinetic energy.
- different forms of energy
- mass- energy equivalence
- principle of conservation of energy

1.4.3 Power

- definition of power
- units of power
- dimension of power
- distinction between work and power

Unit 2: Thermometry and Thermal Expansion

2.1 Heat and temperature

2.2 Thermometry

2.2.1 Mercury thermometer

2.2.2 Thermoelectric thermometer

2.2.3 Radiation thermometer

2.3 Thermal expansion

2.3.1 Linear expansion and its measurement

2.3.2 Cubical expansion and its measurement

2.3.3 Superficial expansion and its measurement

2.4 Transfer of heat

2.4.1 Conduction

2.4.2 Convection

2.4.3 Radiation

Unit 3: Light

3.1 Reflection at plane surfaces

3.2 Reflection at curved mirrors

3.3 Refraction at plane surfaces

3.4 Refraction through prism

3.5 Refraction through lenses

3.6 Dispersion through prism

3.7 Wave theory of light

3.7.1 Huygen's principle

3.7.2 Reflection on the basis of wave theory

3.7.3 Refraction on the basis of wave theory

3.8 Optical instrument

3.8.1 Principle of simple and compound microscope

3.8.2 Telescope

- astronomical
- terrestrial
- Gallelian

Unit 4: Current Electricity

4.1 Ohm's law and its verification

4.2 Resistance in series and parallel

4.3 Rheostat

4.3.1 Thermal effects

4.3.2 Chemical effects

- Faraday's laws

Unit 5: Magnetism

5.1 Atomic view of magnetism

5.2 Bar magnet and lines of magnetic field

5.3 Magnetic pole strength, magnetic length and magnetic dipole moment

5.4 Magnetic field due to bar magnet

5.5 Gauss's law in magnetism

5.6 Terrestrial magnetism

5.6.1 Magnetic elements of the earth

- declination
- dip
- horizontal intensity

5.7 Neutral point

5.8 Tangent law

5.9 Tangent galvanometer

5.10 Deflection magnetometer

5.11 Oscillation magnetometer

5.12 Classification and properties of magnetic elements

5.12.1 Diamagnetic

5.12.2 Paramagnetic

5.12.3 Ferromagnetic

Unit 6: Sound

6.1 Introduction to wave motion

- 6.2 Types of waves
 - 6.2.1 Transverse wave motion
 - 6.2.2 Longitudinal wave motion
- 6.3 Characteristics of a wave motion
- 6.4 Velocity of sound
 - 6.4.1 Speed of transverse wave motion
 - 6.4.2 Speed of longitudinal wave motion
 - 6.4.3 Newton's formula for speed of sound
 - 6.4.4 Laplace's correction
- 6.5 Factors affecting the speed of sound in a gaseous medium
- 6.6 Reflection and refraction of sound

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 80 marks (Pass mark : 28)

Unitwise mark distribution

Units 1 to 3 : 45 marks

Units 4 to 6 : 35 marks

Practical examination : 20 marks (Pass mark : 8)

Mark distribution

Regular performance and record : 4 marks

Experiments in final examination : 12 marks

Oral examination : 4 marks

Prescribed Textbooks

1. Gupta, S. K. Modern's ABC of Physics. New Delhi : New Delhi: Modern Publishers, 1997.
2. Subramanyam, N. and B. Lal. Principles of Physics. New Delhi : S.Chand & Co., 1989.

Reference

1. Rowell, G. and S. Herbert. Physics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995.

Practical

Course Contents

(96 periods)

1. Determination of internal volume of a tube
2. Determination of internal volume of a ball
3. Determination of thickness of a plate
4. Determination of volume of a solid by displacement of water
5. Verification of Archimede's principle
6. Determination of fixed points of a thermometer
7. Determination of melting point of a solid by cooling curve method
8. Verification of law of reflection of light
9. Verification of law of refraction of light
10. Determination of refractive index of glass slab
11. Determination of focal length of a concave mirror
12. Determination of focal length of a convex mirror
13. Determination of velocity of sound in air, in the laboratory by resonance air column method.
14. Comparison of moments of two magnets using oscillation magnetometer
15. Determination of value of dip in laboratory using dip circle
16. Verification of Ohm's law by ammeter and voltmeter
17. Verification of Ohm's law by tangent galvanometer

Prescribed Textbook

1. Shrestha, U. P. Physics Practical Guide. Kathamandu: Ratna Pustak Bhandar, 2050 B.S.

Reference

1. Gupta, S. K. and J. M. Pradhan. Modern Practical Physics. Jalandhar: Surya Publications, 1985.

Chemistry

Course number	: Sc Ed 3002E (S)	Course duration	: 200 hrs (Th120 + Pr80)
Nature of the course	: Theoretical cum Practical	Number of periods	: 240 (Th144 + Pr96)
Full mark	: 100 (Th80 + Pr20)	Periods per week	: Th5 + Pr6 (2x3)
Pass mark	: Th28 + Pr8	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is a special course in chemistry. The course has two parts: theoretical (80%) and practical (20%) and the trainees are required to pass both the parts separately. The theoretical part consists of twelve units that deal with various aspects of chemistry in considerable depth and detail. The practical part deals with the practical applications of the theoretical part.

General Objective

This course is designed to provide the prospective school science teachers with in-depth knowledge of chemistry so that they can run the chemistry classes of secondary level with greater confidence and efficacy. The course also aims at developing manipulative skills needed for practical pedagogical activities in chemistry.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the teacher trainees will be able to

- explain Bohr's model of atom.
- distinguish between orbit and orbital.
- explain quantum numbers.
- explain Pauli's exclusion principle.
- explain the shapes of orbital.
- write electronic configuration of atom.
- interpret different types of chemical reactions.
- explain the rate of chemical reactions.
- explain the factors which affect chemical reactions.
- explain the characteristic features of solutions.

- calculate the concentration of solutions in terms of percentage weight, molarity and normality.
- explain solubility and solubility products.
- explain modern periodic law.
- explain the characteristic features of modern periodic table.
- explain the periodic properties of elements.
- explain the preparation, properties and use of hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, carbon dioxide and ammonia.
- explain the theory of electrolytic dissociation and its factors influencing the dissociation.
- explain chemical bonding.
- interpret acids and bases in terms of Arrhenius, Lewis and Bronsted-Lowry concepts.
- explain the nature of organic and inorganic compounds.
- explain the occurrence, properties and uses of iron, aluminium, copper, silver and gold.
- explain the sources and types of air, water and land pollution.
- explain the effects of air, water and land pollution on human beings and environment.
- explain the sources of noise pollution and its effects on human beings and environment.
- explain the controlling measures of air, water, land and noise pollution.
- explain the types and uses of fertilisers and pesticides.
- explain the harmful effects of fertilisers and pesticides on human beings and environment.
- explain the types and composition of glass and cement.
- explain the different types of plastics.

Course Contents

Unit 1: Atomic Structure	(15 periods)
Unit 2: Ionisation	(10 periods)
Unit 3: Chemical Bonding	(10 periods)
Unit 4: Acids, Bases and Salts	(10 periods)
Unit 5: Chemical Reactions	(5 periods)
Unit 6: Solutions and Solubility	(10 periods)
Unit 7: Periodic Table	(15 periods)
Unit 8: Gases	(10 periods)
Unit 9: Metals	(14 periods)

Unit 10: Introduction to Carbon and its Compounds

Unit 11: Environmental Chemistry

Unit 12: Materials in Daily Life

(5 periods)

(20 periods)

(20 periods)

Course Contents in Detail

Unit 1: Atomic Structure

- 1.1 Bohr's model of the atom
 - 1.1.1 Postulates of Bohr's model of the atom
 - 1.1.2 Successes of Bohr's model
 - 1.1.3 Failures of Bohr's atomic theory
- 1.2 Probability picture of an electron
 - 1.2.1 Concept of atomic orbital
 - 1.2.2 Differences between orbit and orbitals
- 1.3 Quantum numbers
 - 1.3.1 Principal quantum number
 - 1.3.2 Azimuthal quantum number
 - 1.3.3 Magnetic quantum number
 - 1.3.4 Spin quantum number
- 1.4 Pauli's exclusion principle
- 1.5 Shapes of orbital
- 1.6 Electronic configuration of atoms

Unit 2: Ionisation

- 2.1 Theory of electrolytic dissociation
- 2.2 Factors which influence ionisation
- 2.3 Ionisation of water
- 2.4 Electrolysis of water

Unit 3: Chemical Bonding

- 3.1 Electronic theory of valency
- 3.2 Electrovalent bond
- 3.3 Covalent bond
- 3.4 Co-ordinate bond
- 3.5 Characteristics of electrovalent, covalent and co-ordinate compound

Unit 4: Acids, Bases and Salts

- 4.1 Arrhenius theory of acids and bases
- 4.2 Bronsted-Lowry theory of acids and bases
- 4.3 Lewis theory of acids and bases
- 4.4 Types of acids, bases and salts
- 4.5 Neutralisation reactions

Unit 5: Chemical Reactions

- 5.1 Interpreting chemical equations
- 5.2 Types of chemical reactions
- 5.3 Rates of chemical reactions
- 5.4 Conditions which affect the rate of reactions

Unit 6: Solutions and Solubility

- 6.1 Solutions
 - 6.1.1 Characteristics of a solution
 - 6.1.2 Types of solution
 - 6.1.3 Concentration of solution
 - percentage weight
 - molarity
 - normality
- 6.2 Solubility and solubility products
 - 6.2.1 factors that determine solubility
- 6.3 Crystalization

Unit 7: Periodic Table

- 7.1 Modern periodic law
- 7.2 Characteristics of modern periodic table
- 7.3 Periodic properties of elements

Unit 8: Gases

- 8.1 Preparation of H_2 , O_2 , N_2 , CO_2 and NH_3
- 8.2 Properties of H_2 , O_2 , N_2 , CO_2 and NH_3
- 8.3 Uses of H_2 , O_2 , N_2 , CO_2 and NH_3

Unit 9: Metals

- 9.1 Iron
 - 9.1.1 Occurrence
 - 9.1.2 Properties
 - 9.1.3 Uses

- 9.2 Aluminium
 - 9.2.1 Occurrence
 - 9.2.2 Properties
 - 9.2.3 Uses
- 9.3 Copper
 - 9.3.1 Occurrence
 - 9.3.2 Properties
 - 9.3.3 Uses
- 9.4 Silver
 - 9.4.1 Occurrence
 - 9.4.2 Properties
 - 9.4.3 Uses
- 9.5 Gold
 - 9.5.1 Occurrence
 - 9.5.2 Properties
 - 9.5.3 Uses

Unit 10: Introduction to Carbon and its Compounds

- 10.1 Carbon and its structure
- 10.2 Physical and chemical properties of carbon
- 10.3 Organic and inorganic compounds
- 10.4 Introduction to hydrocarbons and its derivatives

Unit 11: Environmental Chemistry

- 11.1 Introduction
- 11.2 Types of pollution
 - 11.2.1 Air pollution
 - Introduction
 - Types of pollutants and their sources
 - Effects of pollution on human beings and environment
 - Control measures
 - 11.2.2 Water pollution
 - Introduction
 - Types of pollutants and their sources
 - Effects of pollution on human beings and environment
 - Control measures

11.2.3 Land pollution

- Introduction
- Types of pollutants and their sources
- Effects of pollution on human beings and environment
- Control measures

11.2.4 Noise pollution

- Introduction
- Types of pollutants and their sources
- Effects of pollution on human beings and environment
- Control measures

Unit 12: Materials in Daily Life

12.1 Fertilisers

12.1.1 Introduction

12.1.2 Types of fertilisers

12.1.3 Uses of fertilisers

12.1.4 Harmful effects of fertilisers

12.2 Pesticides

12.2.1 Introduction

12.2.2 Types of pesticides

12.2.3 Uses of pesticides

12.2.4 Harmful effects of pesticides

12.3 Glass

12.3.1 Introduction

12.3.2 Types of glass

12.3.3 Composition of glass

12.4 Cement

12.4.1 Introduction

12.4.2 Types of cement

12.4.3 Composition of cement

12.5 Plastic

12.5.1 Introduction

12.5.2 Types of plastic

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion

- Individual and group work/project
- Field work
- Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 80 marks (Pass mark : 28)

Unitwise mark distribution

Units 1, 2, 4 and 6	: 25 marks
Units 3, 5, 7, 8 and 9	: 30 marks
Units 10, 11 and 12	: 25 marks

Practical examination : 20 marks (Pass mark : 8)

Mark distribution

Regular performance and record	: 4 marks
Experiments in final examination	: 12 marks
Oral examination	: 4 marks

Prescribed Textbook

1. Jauhar, S. P. Modern's ABC of Chemistry, Volumes I & II. New Delhi: Modern Publishers, 1998.

References

1. Aggarwal, R. C. Modern Inorganic Chemistry. Allahabad: Kitab Mahal, 1979.
2. Matthews, P. Advanced Chemistry. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1992.
3. Peters, E. I. Introduction to Chemical Principles. New York: C. B. S. College Publishing, 1982.
4. Sharma, K. K. and L. K. Sharma. A Textbook of Physical Chemistry. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House, 1986.

Practical

Course Contents (96 periods)

1. Study of the effect of concentration of the rate of reaction between sodium thiosulphate and hydrochloric acid
2. Study of the effect of variation of sodium thiosulphate on the rate of

- reaction
3. Study of the effect of temperature on the rate of reaction between sodium thiosulphate and hydrochloric acid
 4. Preparation of standard solution of oxalic acid from crystalline oxalic acid
 5. Preparation of standard solution of Mohr's salt
 6. Standardisation of the given KMnO_4 solution by titrating it against the standard oxalic acid solution
 7. Standardisation of the given KMnO_4 solution by titrating it against standard Mohr's salt solution
 8. Preparation of the following gases in laboratory and study of their properties
 - 8.1 Hydrogen
 - 8.2 Oxygen
 - 8.3 Carbon dioxide
 - 8.4 Ammonia
 9. Study of solubility products of compounds
 10. Study of crystallisation and recovery of crystals
 11. Study of pH in different kinds of fruit and flowers at different stages
 12. Study of electrolysis of water
 13. Survey of harmful effects of fertilisers in a locality
 14. Survey of harmful effects of pesticides in a locality
 15. Survey of water pollutants in a locality

Prescribed Textbook

1. Giri, S., D. N. Bajpai and O. P. Pandey, Practical Chemistry, New Delhi : S. Chand and Co.

References

1. Chhatwal, G. R., M. Katyal and S. P. Dudeja, Experiments in Chemistry, New Delhi : Tata McGraw Hill.
2. Sthapit, M. K. Elementary Practical Chemistry, Kathmandu: Taleju Prakashan, 1995.

Biology

Course number	: Sc Ed 3003E (S)	Course duration	: 200 hrs (Th120 + Pr80)
Nature of the course	: Theoretical cum Practical	Number of periods	: 240 (Th144 + Pr96)
Full mark	: 100 (Th80 + Pr20)	Periods per week	: Th5 + Pr6 (2x3)
Pass mark	: Th28 + Pr8	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is a special course in biology. The course has two parts: theoretical (80%) and practical (20%) and the trainees are required to pass both the parts separately. The theoretical part consists of ten units that deal with various aspects of biology in considerable depth and detail. The practical part deals with the practical applications of the theoretical part.

General Objective

This course is designed to provide the prospective school science teachers with the basic knowledge of biology including environmental science and develop in them performance skills in carrying out biology curricular activities at the secondary school level.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the trainees will be able to

- explain structures and functions of cells.
- explain mitosis and meiosis cell divisions and their significance.
- explain tissue and tissue system.
- explain the general characteristic features and classification of organisms.
- explain genes and genetic materials
- describe Mendel's law of inheritance.
- explain general concept of linkage crossing over and mutation.
- explain the determining factors of sex.
- explain different types of evolution.
- list the theories of evolution of organic form.

- explain Darwin's theory of evolution.
- explain the different systems of human body.
- explain the structure and reproduction of virus.
- explain symptoms, modes of transmission and controlling measures of viral diseases.
- explain vegetative, asexual and sexual reproduction of plant and animal.
- explain the responses to stimuli in plants and animals.
- explain the organism and environment

Course Contents

Unit 1: Unit of Life	(15 periods)
Unit 2: Tissue and Organs	(15 periods)
Unit 3: Diversity and Classification of Organism	(30 periods)
Unit 4: Language of Life	(30 periods)
Unit 5: Systems of Human Life	(12 periods)
Unit 6: Microbiology	(8 periods)
Unit 7: Reproduction in Biology	(8 periods)
Unit 8: Responses to Stimuli in Plants and Animals	(8 periods)
Unit 9: Organism and Environment	(14 periods)
Unit 10: Environmental Sanitation	(4 periods)

Course Contents in Detail

Unit 1: Unit of Life

- 1.1 Cell structure
 - 1.1.1 Definition of prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells.
 - 1.1.2 Internal structure of prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells.
 - 1.1.3 Functions of cell organelles
 - 1.1.4 Comparison between prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells.
- 1.2 Cell division
 - 1.2.1 Cell division and its significance
 - 1.2.2 Types of cell division
 - mitosis cell division
 - significance of mitosis
 - meiosis cell division
 - significance of meiosis

1.2.3 Comparison of mitosis and meiosis cell division

Unit 2: Tissues and Organs

- 2.1 Definition of tissue
- 2.2 Types of tissues in plants and animals
- 2.3 Structures and functions of tissues in plants and animals
- 2.4 Human organs
 - 2.4.1 Structure and function of the eye
 - 2.4.2 Structure and function of the ear

Unit 3: Diversity and Classification of Organism

- 3.1 Classification of organism
 - 3.1.1 General characteristic features and classification of kingdom monera (prokaryotes)
 - 3.1.2 General characteristic features and classification of kingdom protista up to class (unicellular, eukaryotic)
 - 3.1.3 General characteristic features and classification of kingdom protista up to class (multicellular organism, eukaryotic)
- 3.2 Diversity of organism
 - 3.2.1 Structure and life cycle
 - Spirogyra
 - Mushroom
 - Fern
 - Pinus
 - Pea plant
 - 3.2.2 Structure and life cycle
 - Entamoeba histolytica
 - Silkworm
 - Frog

Unit 4: Language of Life

- 4.1 Heredity, genetics and evolution
 - 4.1.1 Structure and function of chromosome
 - 4.1.2 Chemical nature of chromosome
 - 4.1.3 Definition of gene
 - 4.1.4 Modern concept of gene
 - 4.1.5 Identification of genetic material

- 4.1.6 Structures and functions of DNA (Watson and Crick's model)
- 4.1.7 Differences between DNA and RNA
- 4.1.8 Terminology used in Mendelian laws
- 4.1.9 Mendel's law of inheritance and his experiments
 - interaction between dominant factors
 - complementary factors
 - supplementary factors
 - duple factors
- 4.1.10 General concepts of linkage, crossing over and mutation
- 4.1.11 Determination of sex and sex linkage
- 4.2 Evolution
 - 4.2.1 Definition of evolution
 - 4.2.2 Types of evolution
 - 4.2.3 Introduction to theories on evolution of organic form
 - 4.2.4 Evidence supporting organic evolution
 - 4.2.5 Darwin's theory of evolution
 - 4.2.6 Modern theory of evolution

Unit 5: Systems of Human Life

- 5.1 The skeletal system
 - 5.1.1 Types of bones
 - 5.1.2 Functions of bones
- 5.2 The respiratory system
 - 5.2.1 Organs of respiratory system
 - 5.2.2 Mechanism of respiration
- 5.3 The circulatory system
 - 5.3.1 Composition of the blood
 - 5.3.2 The cardiovascular system
 - the blood vessels
 - the heart (external and internal structure)
 - 5.3.3 Blood circulation
- 5.4 The nervous system
 - 5.4.1 The brain
 - structure
 - central nervous system
 - 5.4.2 peripheral nervous system

Unit 6: Microbiology

- 6.1 Virus and viral diseases
 - 6.1.1 Structure and reproduction of virus
 - 6.1.2 Symptoms, mode of transmission and controlling measures of viral diseases
 - measles
 - polio
 - small pox
 - rabies
 - 6.1.3 Effects of viral diseases on human life
 - 6.1.4 Symptoms, modes of transmission, effects and controlling measures of plant virus
 - tobacco moraic virus (T.M.V.)
 - potato moraic virus (P.M.V.)
 - Bean moraic virus (B.M.V.)

Unit 7: Reproduction in Biology

- 7.1 Reproduction in plants
 - 7.1.1 Vegetative method
 - 7.1.2 Asexual method
 - 7.1.3 Sexual method
- 7.2 Reproduction in animals
 - 7.2.1 Regeneration
 - 7.2.2 Asexual method
 - 7.2.3 Sexual method

Unit 8: Responses to Stimuli in Plants and Animals

- 8.1 Hormones and the regulation of plant growth
- 8.2 Types of growth hormones
- 8.3 Functions of growth hormones
- 8.4 Gravitropism
- 8.5 Photoperiodism
- 8.6 Types of hormones in animals
- 8.7 Functions of hormones in animals

Unit 9: Organism and Environment

- 9.1 Biotic community
 - 9.1.1 Introduction
 - 9.1.2 Characteristics

9.2 Ecosystem

9.2.1 Introduction

9.2.2 Components of ecosystem

- biotic components
- abiotic components

9.2.3 Types of ecosystem

- pond ecosystem
- terrestrial ecosystem

9.2.4 Food chain

- characteristics of food chain
- types of food chain

9.2.5 Food web

- characteristic features of food web
- aquatic food web
- terrestrial food web

9.2.6 Ecological pyramid

9.2.7 Structures and functions of various organisms adapted to aquatic and terrestrial life

Unit 10: Environmental Sanitation

10.1 Introduction

10.2 Solid waste

10.2.1 Sources of solid waste

10.2.2 Types of solid waste

10.2.3 Management of solid waste

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Field work
- Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 80 marks

(Pass mark : 28)

Unitwise mark distribution:

Units 1 to 4	: 50 marks
Units 5 to 8	: 20 marks
Units 9 and 10	: 10 marks

- from collected materials (Division, class and examples)
8. Collection, identification and classification of different types of organism
 9. Study of the structures and symptoms of viral diseases caused by tobacco mosaic virus, potato mosaic virus and bean mosaic virus
 10. Identification of different parts of bones of human body
 11. Study of the ecosystem in the natural environment
 12. Visit solid waste management sites

Prescribed Textbook

1. Kumar, V. *Practical Biology*. New Delhi: Dhanpat Rai and Sons, 1992.

References

1. Pandey, B. P. Modern Practical Botany Volumes I & II. New Delhi: S. Chand and Company, 1995.
2. Verma, P. S. A Manual of Practical Zoology: Invertebrates. New Delhi: S. Chand and Company, 1995.
3. Verma, P. S. A Manual of Practical Zoology: Chordates. New Delhi: S. Chand and Company, 1995.

Fundamentals of Social Studies Education

Course number	: SS Ed 3001	Course duration	: 150 hrs
Nature of the course	: Theoretical	Number of periods	: 180
Full mark	: 100	Periods per week	: 6
Pass mark	: 35	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is an introductory course on social studies education. The course consists of twelve units. The first two units deal with the fundamental concepts of social studies and the rest of the units deal with their applications to classroom teaching.

General Objective

The course aims at acquainting the teacher trainees with the nature and foundation of social studies. In addition, it tries to help them acquire knowledge and develop skills required for the effective teaching of social studies in the secondary schools of Nepal.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the trainees will be able to

- describe the nature and scope of social studies.
- describe the bases of social studies.
- classify educational objectives into major domains.
- present an overview of the current courses of study of social studies at the secondary level in Nepal.
- review the current secondary level textbooks of social studies.
- explain and develop major skills related to the study of social studies.
- apply various methods and techniques in teaching social studies.
- select and use various instructional resources in teaching social studies.
- describe the importance and use of various evaluation devices used in social studies.

- 9.2 Current events
9.3 Controversial issues
9.4 Social studies rooms
9.5 Social studies teachers

Unit 10: Evaluation in Social Studies

- 10.1 Meaning and importance of
- subjective and objective tests
 - observation
 - sociometry
 - attitude test
- 10.2 Construction and use of specification charts

Unit 11: Instructional Planning in Teaching Social Studies

- 11.1 Meaning and importance of
- work plan
 - unit plan
 - lesson plan

Unit 12: Problems and Issues in Social Studies Teaching

- 12.1 Issue of integrating the curriculum
12.2 Problems of implementing the curriculum

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Report writing and classroom presentation
- Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 100 marks

Unitwise mark distribution :

Units 1 and 2	:	30 marks
Units 3 to 6	:	30 marks
Units 7 to 9	:	20 marks
Units 10 to 12	:	20 marks

Questionwise mark distribution :

20 multiple-choice questions	:	20x 1 = 20 marks
2 long-answer questions	:	2x12 = 24 marks
8 short-answer questions	:	8x 7 = 56 marks

Prescribed Textbooks

1. Giri, K. N. and D. Gyawali. Social Studies (2nd edition). Bhotahiti, Kathmandu: Vidhyarthi Pustak Bhandar, 2053 B.S.
2. Pandey, R. K. Teaching Social Studies (2nd edition). Bhotahiti, Kathmandu: Ratna Pustak Bhandar, 2050 B.S.

References

1. Aggarwal, J. C. Teaching of Social Studies (2nd edition). New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House, 1993.
2. Jarolimik, J. Social Studies in Elementary Education. New York: Macmillan, 1963.
3. Kochar, S. R. The Teaching of Social Studies. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers, 1995.
4. Kohli, A. S. Teaching of Social Studies. New Delhi: Anmol Publications, 1996.
5. Ministry of Educaiton, HMG. Secondary School Curriculum. Sanothimi, Bhaktapur: Curriculum Development Centre, Ministry of Education.
6. Ministry of Educaiton, HMG. Social Studies Textbooks (Grades VI to X). Sanothimi, Bhaktapur: Curriculum Development Centre, Ministry of Education.
7. Thakur, I. D. Teaching of Social Studies. Bhotahiti, Kathmandu: Ratna Pustak Bhandar, 2053 B.S.

Teaching Social Studies I

Course number	: SS Ed 3002	Course duration	: 150 (75+75) hrs
Nature of the course	: Theoretical	Number of periods	: 180 (90+90)
Full mark	: 100 (50+50)	Periods per week	: 6 (3+3)
Pass mark	: 36 (18+18)	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is a course on teaching geographic and economic components within social studies. The course consists of two parts, each having nine units. Part A deals with teaching geography components and Part B deals with teaching economics components. The first three units of each part focus on the concepts of the concerned discipline and the rest of the units concentrate on their pedagogical applications. The teacher trainees are required to pass both the parts separately.

General Objective

The course aims at providing the teacher trainees with the knowledge of various concepts of geography and economics and developing in them the pedagogical skills required for the effective teaching of these two components of social studies in the secondary schools of Nepal.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the teacher trainees will be able to

- define geography and economics and describe their scope.
- differentiate geography and economics from geography education and economics education respectively.
- list the concepts of geography and economics included in the secondary level course on social studies.
- formulate instructional objectives in behavioural terms from the concerned units of the secondary level course on social studies.
- set the strategies for teaching basic themes of the concerned units.
- prepare and use different types of charts in teaching concerned units.

- construct various test items from the concerned units.
- prepare and use unit and lesson plans for teaching different units of the course.
- develop competencies in teaching concerned units through microteaching.

Course Contents

Part A : Teaching Geography Components

Unit 1: Geography as a Discipline	(14 periods)
Unit 2: Geography Education	(6 periods)
Unit 3: Geographical Concepts in Social Studies	(8 periods)
Unit 4: Instructional Objectives in Geography Components	(6 periods)
Unit 5: Strategies of Teaching Geography Components	(14 periods)
Unit 6: Teaching Aids for Geography Components	(12 periods)
Unit 7: Construction of Test Items on Geography Components	(10 periods)
Unit 8: Instructional Planning of Geography Components	(10 periods)
Unit 9: Microteaching in Geography Components	(10 periods)

Part B : Teaching Economics Components

Unit 1: Economics as a Discipline	(16 periods)
Unit 2: Economics Education	(8 periods)
Unit 3: Economic Concepts in Social Studies	(8 periods)
Unit 4: Instructional Objectives in Economics Components	(6 periods)
Unit 5: Strategies of Teaching Economics Components	(12 periods)
Unit 6: Teaching Aids for Economics Components	(12 periods)
Unit 7: Construction of Test Items on Economics Components	(8 periods)
Unit 8: Instructional Planning of Economics Components	(10 periods)
Unit 9: Microteaching in Economics Components	(10 periods)

Course Contents in Detail

Part A : Teaching Geography Components

Unit 1: Geography as a Discipline

- 1.1 Definition of geography
- 1.2 Nature and scope of geography
- 1.3 Relation of geography with physical and social sciences

Unit 2: Geography Education

- 2.1 Meaning of geography education
- 2.2 Distinction between geography education and geography
- 2.3 Aims and objectives of geography education

Unit 3: Geographical Concepts in Social Studies

- 3.1 Study of geographical concepts in the social studies courses of Grades VI to X

Unit 4: Instructional Objectives in Geography Components

- 4.1 Formulation of instructional objectives

Unit 5: Strategies of Teaching Geography Components

- 5.1 Teaching physical geography
- 5.2 Teaching human geography
- 5.3 Teaching regional geography
- 5.4 Teaching local geography

Unit 6: Teaching Aids for Geography Components

- 6.1 Maps and globes
 - 6.1.1 Reading and using maps and globes
 - 6.1.2 Construction of maps based on concerned units
 - 6.1.3 Map filling (Nepal)

Unit 7: Construction of Test Items on Geography Components

- 7.1 Construction of different types of subjective questions
- 7.2 Construction of different types of objective questions
- 7.3 Construction of test items to measure skills of reading maps and globes

Unit 8: Instructional Planning of Geography Components

- 8.1 Preparation of unit plans
- 8.2 Preparation of lesson plans

Unit 9: Microteaching in Geography Components

- 9.1 microteaching in the peer group

✓ **Part B : Teaching Economics Components**

Unit 1: Economics as a Discipline

- 1.1 Changing concepts of economics
1.2 Scope and methodology of economics
1.3 Relationship of economics with other social sciences

Unit 2: Economics Education

- 2.1 Meaning, role and objectives of economics education
2.2 Differences between economics education and economics

Unit 3: Economic Concepts in Social Studies

- 3.1 Study of economic concepts in the social studies courses of Grades VI to X

Unit 4: Instructional Objectives in Economics Components

- 4.1 Formulation of instructional objectives

Unit 5: Strategies of Teaching Economics Components

- 5.1 Teaching economic interdependence
5.2 Teaching population resources and environment and their relationship

Unit 6: Teaching Aids for Economics Components

- 6.1 Construction and use of
- line graphs
 - simple bar, multiple bar and sub-divided bar diagrams
 - pie and pyramidal diagrams

Unit 7: Construction of Test Items on Economics Components

- 7.1 Construction of different types of subjective questions
7.2 Construction of different types of objective questions

Unit 8: Instructional Planning of Economics Components

- 8.1 Preparation of unit plans
8.2 Preparation of lesson plans

Unit 9: **Microteaching in Economics Components**
9.1 Microteaching in the peer group

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Report writing and classroom presentation
- Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 100 marks

Partwise and unitwise mark distribution

Part A : 50 marks

Units 1 to 3 : 15 marks

Units 4 to 6 : 20 marks

Units 7 to 9 : 15 marks

Part B : 50 marks

Units 1 to 3 : 20 marks

Units 4 to 6 : 15 marks

Units 7 to 9 : 15 marks

Questionwise mark distribution (identical in both parts)

10 multiple-choice questions : $10 \times 1 = 10$ marks

1 long-answer question : $1 \times 12 = 12$ marks

4 short-answer questions : $4 \times 7 = 28$ marks

Prescribed Textbooks

1. Gyawali, D. Geography Teaching. Kathmandu: Vidyarathi Pustak Bhandar, 1996.
2. Kushiyat, B. K. Arthashastra Shikshan Bidhi. Kathmandu: Ratna Pustak Bhandar, (latest edition).
3. Pandey, R. K. Geography Education. Kathmandu: Ratna Pustak Bhandar, 1992.

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References

1. Ministry of Educaiton, HMG. Secondary School Curriculum. Sanothimi, Bhaktapur: Curriculum Development Centre, Ministry of Education.
2. Ministry of Educaiton, HMG. Social Studies Textbooks (Grades VI to X). Sanothimi, Bhaktapur: Curriculum Development Centre, Ministry of Education.
3. Siddique, M. H. Teaching of Economics. New Delhi: Ashish Publishing House, 1993.
4. Yadav, A. Teaching of Economics. New Delhi: Anmol Publications, 1995.

✓ Teaching Social Studies II

Course number	: SS Ed 3003	Course duration	: 150 (75+75) hrs
Nature of the course	: Theoretical	Number of periods	: 180 (90+90)
Full mark	: 100 (50+50)	Periods per week	: 6 (3+3)
Pass mark	: 36 (18+18)	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is a course on teaching political science and history components within social studies. The course consists of two parts, each having nine units. Part A deals with teaching political science components and Part B deals with teaching history components. The first three units of each part focus on the concepts of the concerned discipline while the rest of the units concentrate on their pedagogical aspects. The teacher trainees are required to pass both the parts separately.

General Objective

The course aims at providing the teacher trainees with the knowledge of various concepts of political science and history and developing in them the pedagogical skills required for the effective teaching of these two components of social studies in the secondary schools of Nepal.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the teacher trainees will be able to

- define political science and history and describe their scope.
- differentiate political science and history from political science education and history education respectively.
- lists the concepts of political science and history included in the secondary level course on social studies.
- formulate instructional objectives in behavioural terms from the concerned units of the secondary level course on social studies.
- set the strategies for teaching basic themes of the concerned units.
- prepare and use different types of charts in teaching concerned units.

12

- construct various test items from the concerned units.
- prepare and use unit and lesson plans for teaching different units of the course.
- develop competencies in teaching concerned units through microteaching.

Course Contents

Part A : Teaching Political Science Components

- Unit 1: Political Science as a Discipline (16 periods)
- Unit 2: Political Science Education (6 periods)
- Unit 3: Political Science Concepts in Social Studies (8 periods)
- Unit 4: Instructional Objectives in Political Science Components (6 periods)
- Unit 5: Strategies of Teaching Political Science Components (12 periods)
- Unit 6: Teaching Aids for Political Science Components (8 periods)
- Unit 7: Construction of Test Items on Political Science Components (10 periods)
- Unit 8: Instructional Planning of Political Science Components (12 periods)
- Unit 9: Microteaching in Political Science Components (12 periods)

Part B : Teaching History Components

- Unit 1: History as a Discipline (16 periods)
- Unit 2: History Education (5 periods)
- Unit 3: Historical Concepts in Social Studies (8 periods)
- Unit 4: Instructional Objectives in History Components (6 periods)
- Unit 5: Strategies of Teaching History Components (15 periods)
- Unit 6: Teaching Aids for History Components (6 periods)
- Unit 7: Construction of Test Items on History Components (10 periods)
- Unit 8: Instructional Planning of History Components (12 periods)
- Unit 9: Microteaching in History Components (12 periods)

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Course Contents in Detail

✓ **Part A : Teaching Political Science Components**

Unit 1: Political Science as a Discipline

- 1.1 Changing concepts of political science
 - 1.1.1 Meaning
 - 1.1.2 Scope
 - 1.1.3 Methodology
- 1.2 Relation of political science with other social sciences

Unit 2: Political Science Education

- 2.1 Meaning of political science education
- 2.2 Distinction of political science education from political education and the education of political science
- 2.3 Purposes of political science education

Unit 3: Political Science Concepts in Social Studies

- 3.1 Study of political science concepts in the social studies courses of Grades VI to X

Unit 4: Instructional Objectives in Political Science Components

- 4.1 Formulation of instructional objectives

Unit 5: Strategies of Teaching Political Science Components

- 5.1 Teaching civic sense
- 5.2 Teaching social evils and problems
- 5.3 Teaching international understanding

Unit 6: Teaching Aids for Political Science Components

- 6.1 Construction and use of
 - organisation charts
 - classification charts
 - flow charts
 - comparative charts
 - descriptive charts

Unit 7: Construction of Test Items on Political Science Components

- 7.1 Construction of different types of subjective questions
- 7.2 Construction of different types of objective questions

Unit 8: Instructional Planning of Political Science Components

- 8.1 Preparation of unit plans
- 8.2 Preparation of lesson plans

Unit 9: Microteaching in Political Science Components

- 9.1 Microteaching in the peer group

- Part B : Teaching History Components

Unit 1: History as a Discipline

- 1.1 Changing concepts of history
- 1.2 Scope of history
- 1.3 Relation of history with other social sciences

Unit 2: History Education

- 2.1 Nature of history education
- 2.2 Differences between history education and history
- 2.3 Purposes of history education

Unit 3: Historical Concepts in Social Studies

- 3.1 Study of historical concepts in the social studies courses of Grades VI to X

Unit 4: Instructional Objectives in History Components

- 4.1 Formulation of instructional objectives

Unit 5: Strategies of Teaching History Components

- 5.1 Teaching national heroes of Nepal
- 5.2 Teaching socio-economic history of Nepal
- 5.3 Teaching political history of Nepal and the world
- 5.4 Teaching world civilisations

Unit 6: Teaching Aids for History Components

- 6.1 Construction and use of
 - genealogy charts
 - time charts

Unit 7: Construction of Test Items on History Components

- 7.1 Construction of various types of subjective questions
- 7.2 Construction of various types of objective questions

Unit 8: Instructional Planning of History Components

- 8.1 Preparation of unit plans
- 8.2 Preparation of lesson plans

Unit 9: Microteaching in History Components

- 9.1 Microteaching in the peer group

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Report writing and classroom presentation
- Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 100 marks

Partwise and unitwise mark distribution :

Part A : 50 marks

Units 1 to 3 : 20 marks

Units 4 to 6 : 15 marks

Units 7 to 9 : 15 marks

Part B : 50 marks

Units 1 to 3 : 20 marks

Units 4 to 6 : 15 marks

Units 7 to 9 : 15 marks

Questionwise mark distribution (identical in both parts) :

10 multiple-choice questions : $10 \times 1 = 10$ marks

1 long-answer question : $1 \times 12 = 12$ marks

4 short-answer questions : $4 \times 7 = 28$ marks

Prescribed Textbooks

1. Quaiyum, Abdul. Rajniti Shastra Shikshan Bidhi. Bhotahiti, Kathmandu: Vidhyarthi Pustak Bhandar, 2052 B.S.
2. Upadhyaya, S. R. Itihas Shikshan Bidhi. Bhotahiti, Kathmandu: Ratna Pustak Bhandar, 2050 B.S.

References

1. Aggarwal, J. C. Teaching of Social Studies (2nd edition). New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House, 1993.
2. Kohli, A. S. Teaching of Social Studies. New Delhi: Anmol Publications, 1996.
3. Ministry of Educaiton, HMG. Secondary School Curriculum. Sanothimi, Bhaktapur: Curriculum Development Centre, Ministry of Education.
4. Ministry of Educaiton, HMG. Social Studies Textbooks (Grades VI to X). Sanothimi, Bhaktapur: Curriculum Development Centre, Ministry of Education.

